

INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE FEMALE SEX.

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Abstract: Inflammatory diseases of women are the first among gynecological diseases. In this disease, anatomical and physiological features of the female body have a special place. In particular, the proximity of the genitals to external influences, monthly cyclical changes depending on the menstrual function, abortion and damage to the reproductive tract tissue during childbirth are among them. In addition, during pregnancy, a decrease in the body's resistance to various negative effects of the external environment, tissue damage, operative interventions, combined with posthemorrhagic anemia, cause the development of the inflammatory process. Factors that reduce the body's resistance include mental and physical exhaustion, colds, flu, and others.

Key words: Gynecological inflammatory diseases, pelvioperitonitis, salpingoophoritis, cytomegalovirus, vulvitis.

The causative microbe plays an important role in the pathogenesis of acute and moderate inflammatory diseases. As soon as it passes, the body's resistance reaction aimed at limiting the focus of inflammation starts. In the chronic stages of the disease, the causative microbe loses its pathogenetic significance. Specific changes in the genital organs of women with inflammatory diseases are as follows: Pain is one of the constant symptoms. Impulses arising as a result of exposure to the genitals reach the cerebral cortex through the spinal cord, where they are processed into a pain sensation. Pain in inflammatory processes depends on many factors (scarring processes) and physico-chemical influence of pain receptors (metabolic disorders, intoxication). Features of pain:

- when the inflammatory process passes to the pelvic peritoneum, the pain is stronger than in metroendometritis;
- in the acute stage of the inflammatory process, the level of pain is moderate, more intense than in the chronic stage;
- the intensity of pain depends on the nature of the stimulus causing inflammation;
- pain increases before menstruation, during menstruation, during cold and during physical exertion.

Violation of menstrual function. These disorders are accompanied by hyperpolymenorrhea, metrorrhagia. Acyclic bleeding is caused not only by ovarian dysfunction caused by inflammation of the genitals, but also by tumors. Sexual function. Pain during sex is associated with inflammation of the uterus, connective tissue, pelvic floor and peritoneum. Bloody discharge during sexual intercourse (contact bleeding) is observed in cervical polyp, colpitis, endocervicitis in cervical erosion (except for cancer).

Vulvitis in women of reproductive age, vulvitis often occurs as a result of colpitis, cervicitis, and endometritis, as a result of infection of the external genital organs by pathogenic microorganisms contained in vaginal secretions. The development of primary vulvitis is caused by cutting, non-observance of external genital hygiene, chemical, thermal, mechanical effects, endocrine diseases, inflammatory diseases in the perianal area. The secondary process often has the character of vulvovaginitis. In the acute phase, vulvitis is characterized by hyperemia, swelling, serous purulent and purulent coating of the external genitalia. Subjective complaints include: pain, burning, general weakness. In the chronic stage of vulvitis, hyperemia, swelling, exudation, itching decrease, but periodically recur. The cure. It is necessary to take a bath with a decoction of kokiot, use antibacterial ointments, and treat related diseases.

Vulvovaginitis (Lat. vulva - external genital organ, vagina - vagina, dog - inflammation) is inflammation of female external genital organs and vagina. In this case, a lot of waste begins to be released from the vagina, the vulva area itches and hurts, the pain increases when walking, the skin of the external genitalia, sometimes the inner surface of the thighs and buttocks reddens. If treated on time, the patient will recover quickly. In delayed cases, the disease takes on a chronic nature and often recurs, adhesions of the front and back walls of the vagina, adhesions between the labia are observed in 3-4-year-old girls. Vulvovaginitis is caused by various microbes (often, staphylococcus, streptococcus, Escherichia coli, sometimes diphtheria bacillus) and fungi. The origin of the disease is related to violation of personal hygiene rules, damage to the skin of the vulva and mucous membrane of the vagina (inflammation, itching), the effects of seizures, as well as various chronic diseases that weaken the body's protective function (tonsillitis, pyelonephritis) and metabolic disorders. can be caused by diseases (obesity, diabetes). The cure. Increasing the body's immunity, primary infection foci are sanitized; the vagina is rinsed with local remedies, antibiotic therapy is carried out.

Endocervicitis is an inflammation of the mucous membrane of the cervical canal, which can be caused by staphylococci, streptococci, gonococci, and Escherichia coli. Endocervicitis is caused by diseases that reduce the overall strength of the body, tearing of the cervix, the hiatus during childbirth, prolapse of the internal genitals, chemical and thermal exposure, and burns. There are acute, moderately acute and chronic stages of endocervicitis. In acute endocervitis, there is redness and swelling around the cervix. Purulent or muco-purulent discharge comes from the cervical canal. When the disease progresses to moderately acute and chronic stages, the redness and swelling decrease, the discharge becomes muco-purulent, and then mucoid.

After viewing the external genitalia, the vagina and cervix are in the mirrors A thorough anamnesis is performed to determine the etiology of the disease collection, careful examination of patients, necessary bacteriological and bacterioscopic examinations should be carried out

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